

Measurements of Activity Coefficients of Tetra-alkyl Ammonium Salts in Aqueous Solutions

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Clay membrane electrodes have been utilised for the determination of activity coefficients of tetramethyl-ammonium iodide and tetraethyl-ammonium iodide in aqueous solutions. The range of concentration measurable with such electrodes for both the salts is 0.0001 m to 0.1 m.

The measurement of activity and activity coefficients of tetra-alkyl ammonium salts has been a subject of discussion in recent years in view of the discrepancies in the observed data by different methods^{1-6, 11, 12}.

Clay membrane electrodes are suitable for the activity measurements of a variety of cations including NH_4^+ (Cf. Marshall et al⁷, Adhikari⁸). In the present work these electrodes have been utilised for the activity measurements of tetra-alkyl ammonium salts. The action of the clay membranes as reversible electrodes appears to be dependent on the exchangeability of the cation on the surface of the membrane material. Since the cations differ in exchangeability often quite markedly, the ranges of their activity registered by membrane electrodes are different. When the solutions are fairly dilute and the ratio of concentrations in the two solutions of the same ions is kept within one-tenth or one-third, the observed e. m. f. should correspond to the Nernst equation,

$$E = \frac{RT}{nf} \ln \frac{m_2 \gamma_{+2}}{m_1 \gamma_{+1}}$$

sat. calomel, $\text{R}_4\text{N}^+\text{X}^-$
 m, γ_{+1}

Membrane

for a cell set up of the type
 $\text{R}_4\text{N}^+\text{X}^-$, calomel sat.
 $m_2 \gamma_{+2}$

where R_4N^+ = quaternary ammonium ion, X^- = halide ion.

If γ_{+1} is calculated for extremely dilute solution by the Debye-Hückel limiting equation for uniunivalent electrolyte, $\log \gamma_{+1} = -0.509 \sqrt{\mu}$, knowledge of m_1, γ_{+1}, m_2 and E would give the value for γ_{+2} . By setting up a series of cells of this type with

1. M. A. V. Devanathan and M. J. Fernando, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 19 2, 58, 784.
2. L. Ebert and J. Lange, *Z. Physik. Chim.*, 1928, 139A, 584, 1934, 168A, 147.
3. J. H. Jones, F. J. Spuhler and W. A. Felsing, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 965.
4. R. H. Stokes, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 761.
5. B. E. Conway, *Electrochemical Data*, Elsevier Pub. 1952, page 90, Bowler Road, Thesis, London University, 1960.

different concentrations of tetra-alkyl-ammonium salt, the measured E values may be used to evaluate the ionic activity coefficient of these salts at any desired concentration. With this background an attempt has been made to evaluate the ionic activity coefficients of tetra-alkyl-ammonium iodides such as tetramethyl and tetraethyl at different concentrations at 25°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental procedure for membrane preparation and use for activity measurement was similar to that reported previously.⁸ Preliminary experiments showed that Padegaon and Aquagel Ca-form of membranes heated at 600° were best suited for the present purpose. The entire cell composed of the membrane electrodes and two tiny identical saturated calomel electrodes in two solutions separated by the membrane, was placed in a 25° ± 0.5° thermostat. Equilibrium e.m.f. values were noted after ascertaining, as usual, absence of asymmetry potential. The ratio of the concentration of the electrolyte was kept at either 1 : 10 or 1 : 3. Usually the average of two sets of readings not differing by 0.05 m.v. is recorded. The tetramethyl-ammonium iodide and tetraethyl-ammonium iodide were products of B.D.H. or Light & Co. These salts were further purified by recrystallisation twice from aqueous ethyl alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The concentration of the solution prepared was determined by the conductometric titration of the iodide salt with silver nitrate solution.

T A B L E I

Tetraethyl-ammonium Iodide

Concentration (molality)	E. M. F. observed in m. v.		γ_{\pm} observed
	P*	A*	
0.0001 m	57.8	57.8	0.9360 at
.001 m			.001 m
0.001 m	57.25	57.25	0.868 at
0.01 m			0.01 m
0.1 m	52.9	52.95	0.6797 at
.01 m			0.1 m
0.03 m	26.05	26.1	0.797 at
0.01 m			0.03 m
0.02 m	16.5	16.55	0.825 at
0.01 m			0.02 m
.01 m	62.0	62.05	0.4835 at
.2 m			0.2 m
0.02 m	45.15	45.1	0.4772 at
0.2 m			0.2 m

*P, Padegaon membrane ; *A, Aquagel membrane.

6. V. E. Bower and R. A. Robinson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 1717.
7. C. E. Marshall and W. E. Bergman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1911.
8. M. Adhikari, *Jour. India n Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 817.
9. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1956 p. 124.

TABLE II

Tetramethyl-ammonium Iodide

Concentration (molality)	E. M. F. observed in m, v.		γ_+ observed
	P*	A*	
0.0001 m	57.8	57.8	.9360 at 0.001 m
<u>.001 m</u>			
.001 m	57.5	57.55	0.877 at 0.01 m
<u>0.01 m</u>			
0.1 m	53.2	53.25	0.6942 at 0.1 m
<u>0.01 m</u>			
0.03 m	26.05	26.00	0.806 at 0.03 m
<u>0.01 m</u>			

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The activity coefficients of tetraethyl-ammonium and tetramethyl-ammonium iodide solutions are given in Tables I and II respectively. The activity coefficients of both these salts at 0.0001 m solution were calculated by using Debye-Hückel limiting equation. On the basis of the calculated values of $\gamma_+ = 0.9886$ at 0.0001 m, the activity coefficients of these salts at other concentrations were calculated from the observed e.m.f. It will be seen from Table I that the activity coefficient of tetraethyl-ammonium iodide at 0.1 m solution comes out to be 0.6797, whereas the values reported by Bower and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) and by Lindenbaum and Boyd¹⁰ are 0.685 and 0.683 respectively. The present value is thus in close agreement with those reported by these group of workers but is different from that reported by Conway (*loc. cit.*). However, the calculated activity coefficients of 0.2 m solution show an anomaly by the same technique but using two sets of solutions. Thus, using 0.02 m/0.2m and 0.01 m/0.2 m, the values obtained were 0.4772 and 0.483 respectively (*cf.* Table I). These values differ from that reported by Conway, Bower and Robinson for 0.2 m solution and the discrepancy refers to the limitation of membrane electrodes for activity measurements at higher concentration range. It may be said that the range of validity of the Nernst equation with membrane electrode for activity measurements of tetraethyl-ammonium salt is 0.0001 m – 0.1 m.

The activity coefficients of tetramethyl-ammonium iodide is slightly higher in comparison to tetraethyl-ammonium iodide and the value for 0.1 m solution for this salt is in close agreement with the value reported by Lindenbaum and Boyd (*loc. cit.*) and Levien¹². The higher values of activity coefficients of this salt compared to the tetraethyl-ammonium iodide has been explained by Lindenbaum *et al.* on the basis of formation of water structure around the cation. The concentration range measurable for the latter is 0.0001 m to 0.1 m.

10. S. Lindenbaum and G. E. Boyd., *J. Phys. Chem.* 1964, **68**, 911.
11. E. L. Swarts and C. A. Kraus, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, **40**, 382.
12. B. J. Levien, *Australian J. Chem.*, 1965, **18**, 1161.

It thus appears from the above discussion that the clay membrane electrode is a suitable tool for determining the activity coefficients of tetra-alkyl-ammonium salts in dilute aqueous solutions within a limited range of concentration.

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Received, February 28, 1968.